

PHYSICS AND MATHEMATICS

SOLUTION OF A MIXED PROBLEM FOR A LOADED HEAT EQUATION

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ABSTRACT

The mixed problem considered in the presented work is of practical importance. Its mathematical model is related to the construction of a new model of the heat transfer process loaded at n points. It is more characteristic to obtain an algebraic condition for the parameter μ in the loading coefficient. [2], [7]

Keywords: Loaded heat equation, mixed problem, spectral problem, eigenfunction, eigenvalues

INTRODUCTION

One-dimensional heat transfer and diffusion equations occupy an important place as a subset of the class of partial differential equations of practical importance. It should be noted that loaded equations and problems associated with these equations are a special section of this class [1], [2]. The problem under consideration covers a small part of this section. This section is based on the simultaneous consideration of boundary and Cauchy problems for the loaded one-dimensional heat transfer equation [7]. The model of many diffusion and heat transfer processes in nature is reduced to the study of the solution of problems with initial and boundary conditions for loaded second-order parabolic equations.

1. STATEMENT OF THE MIXED PROBLEM FOR THE LOADED PARABOLIC EQUATION

Consider the loaded heat equation

$$u_t = a^2 u_{xx} + \sum_{j=1}^l b_j u(x, j) \quad (1)$$

Note that here $0 < x < 1, t > 0, \mu$ is parameter.

Let's add to equation boundary conditions

$$\left. \begin{aligned} u(0, t) &= 0 \\ u(1, t) &= 0 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (2)$$

and initial conditions

$$u(x, 0) = \varphi(x) \quad (3)$$

(1)-(3) is called mixed problem [7]

2. ON EIGENVALUES AND EIGENFUNCTIONS OF THE SPECTRAL PROBLEM

Based on the mentioned mixed problem, the corresponding spectral problem is formulated [4], [6]:

$$\begin{aligned} y'' &= -\lambda^2 y, \\ y(0) &= 0, y(1) = 0 \end{aligned}$$

Now let's look at the general solution of a second-order ordinary differential equation depending on a parameter:

$$y(x) = C_1 \cos \lambda x + C_2 \sin \lambda x.$$

The boundary conditions of the spectral problem must be satisfied from this solution. The eigenvalues of the spectral problem under consideration are found in the form $\lambda_n = \pi n, n \in N$. The eigenfunctions of the spectral problem are written as follows:

$$y_n(x) = C_2 \sin \pi n x, n \in N.$$

It can be easily found that the defined eigenfunctions form an orthogonal system in $C[0,1]$. If $C_2 = \pm\sqrt{2}$, then in the mentioned space the orthogonal system is reduced to an orthonormalized system. Then we can take the eigenfunctions as

$$y_n(x) = \sqrt{2} \sin \pi n x, n \in N. \quad (4)$$

The eigenfunctions form a complete system in the space $C[0,1]$. Hence, we can expand by series functions $\varphi(x)$ and $u(x, t)$ according to their eigenfunctions:

$$\varphi(x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \varphi_n y_n(x),$$

here φ_n is found as we have noted below.

$$\varphi_n = \int_0^1 \varphi(x) y_n(x) dx, n=1,2,3\dots$$

$$u(x, t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} u_n(t) y_n(x). \quad (5)$$

If we look at the expression of the function $u(x, t)$ that we will note:

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} u'_n(t)y_n(x) = a^2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} u_n(t)y_n''(x) + \mu \sum_{j=1}^l b_j \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} u_n(j)y_n(x),$$

taking into account, that $y_n''(x) = -\lambda_n^2 y_n(x)$, following is true:

$$\left[\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} u'_n(t) - a^2 \lambda_n^2 u_n(t) + \mu \sum_{j=1}^l b_j u_n(j) \right] y_n(x) = 0,$$

$n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$

Thus, here

$$u'_n(t) + a^2 \lambda_n^2 u_n(t) = \mu \sum_{j=1}^l b_j u_n(j) \tag{6}$$

$$u'_n(t) = \varphi_n(x). \tag{7}$$

In this way, a Cauchy problem consisting of a computationally large number of loaded linear differential equations of the same order is obtained. Taking these into account, it is possible to write the solution of the linear differential equation (6) as follows:

$$u_n(t) = e^{-a^2 \lambda_n^2 t} \left[c_n + \int_0^t \sum_{j=1}^l b_j u_n(j) e^{a^2 \lambda_n^2 \tau} d\tau \right].$$

Taking into account initial conditions we can see, that $c_n = \varphi_n$. Therefore, we find the solution to the Cauchy problem (6)-(7) as follows:

$$u_n(t) = e^{-a^2 \lambda_n^2 t} \left[\varphi_n + \mu \sum_{j=1}^l b_j \frac{1}{a^2 \lambda_n^2} (e^{a^2 \lambda_n^2 t} - 1) u_n(j) \right] \tag{8}$$

3. FINDING FOURIER COEFFICIENTS THROUGH A SYSTEM OF ALGEBRAIC EQUATIONS

In accordance with what we mentioned above, let's consider the values $t = 1, 2, 3, \dots, l$ in the following expressions:

$$u_n(1) = e^{-a^2 \lambda_n^2} \left[\varphi_n + \mu \sum_{j=1}^l b_j \frac{1}{a^2 \lambda_n^2} (e^{a^2 \lambda_n^2} - 1) u_n(j) \right],$$

$$u_n(l) = e^{-a^2 \lambda_n^2 l} \left[\varphi_n + \mu \sum_{j=1}^l b_j \frac{1}{a^2 \lambda_n^2} (e^{a^2 \lambda_n^2 l} - 1) u_n(j) \right].$$

If we multiply both sides of the first equation by $e^{a^2 \lambda_n^2}$ and simultaneously both sides of the last equation by $e^{a^2 \lambda_n^2 l}$, then we get

$$e^{a^2 \lambda_n^2} u_n(1) = \varphi_n + \frac{1}{a^2 \lambda_n^2} (e^{a^2 \lambda_n^2} - 1) \mu \sum_{j=1}^l b_j u_n(j),$$

$$e^{a^2 \lambda_n^2 l} u_n(l) = \varphi_n + \frac{1}{a^2 \lambda_n^2} \left[(e^{a^2 \lambda_n^2 l} - 1) \mu \sum_{j=1}^l b_j u_n(j) \right].$$

After that after multiplying both sides of these equalities by $a^2 \lambda_n^2$ we get :

$$a^2 \lambda_n^2 e^{a^2 \lambda_n^2} u_n(1) = a^2 \lambda_n^2 \varphi_n + (e^{a^2 \lambda_n^2} - 1) \mu \sum_{j=1}^l b_j u_n(j)$$

... ..

$$a^2 \lambda_n^2 e^{a^2 \lambda_n^2 l} u_n(l) = a^2 \lambda_n^2 \varphi_n + (e^{a^2 \lambda_n^2 l} - 1) \mu \sum_{j=1}^l b_j u_n(j)$$

Let's transform the obtained system using the rule mentioned below:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \left[b_1 (e^{a^2 \lambda_n^2} - 1) \mu - a^2 \lambda_n^2 e^{a^2 \lambda_n^2} u_n \right] u_n(1) + \\ \left(e^{a^2 \lambda_n^2} - 1 \right) \mu \sum_{j=1}^l b_j u_n(j) = -a^2 \lambda_n^2 \varphi_n \\ \dots \dots \dots \dots \dots \\ \left(e^{a^2 \lambda_n^2} - 1 \right) \mu \sum_{j=1}^{l-1} b_j u_n(j) + \\ \left[(e^{a^2 \lambda_n^2 l} - 1) \mu - a^2 \lambda_n^2 e^{a^2 \lambda_n^2 l} \right] u_n(l) = -a^2 \lambda_n^2 \varphi_n \end{array} \right.$$

From the last system we get expressions for $u_n(1), u_n(2), \dots, u_n(l)$. If we expand the main determinant of this system in μ we obtain a polynomial of the first degree.. The polynomial under consideration has one root. Outside this root, the main determinant of the system is nonzero Since the system is linear with respect to $u_n(1),$

Loaded heat (5 spatial points) | SciPy expm=True

$$l = 10, \mu = x(1 - x)$$

Loaded heat (10 spatial points) | SciPy expm=True

CONCLUSION

This paper presents a mixed problem for the heat equation with loads at n points over time. An algebraic condition for the existence of a solution of considering problem for the load parameter μ is found, and a computer implementation of the mixed-problem is presented, which is practically equivalent to the geometric description in the paper. However, the present paper has physical meaning for the loaded heat equation.

References

1. Khankishiyev Z.F. Solution of one problem for a loaded differential equation by the method of finite differences. *Applied and Computational Mathematics*, 2022, vol. 21, №2, pp. 147–157.
2. Khankishiyev Z.F. Solution of one problem for a parabolic type linear loaded differential equation. *The Reports of National Academy of Sciences of Azerbaijan*, 2022, Volume LXXVIII, №1–2, pp. 8–13.
3. Khankishiyev Z.F. Solution of one problem for linear loaded parabolic type of differential equation

with integral conditions. *Advanced Mathematical Models and Applications*, 2022, vol. 7, №2, pp. 178–190.

4. Isgandarov E.Sh., Ahmadov S.Z., Ahmadov H.I. On Finding a Solution of One Problem for the Heat Equation on a Semi-Axis. *Journal of Physical Mathematics & its Applications*, 2025, vol. 3, no. 5, pp. 1–5.

5. Khankishiyev Z.F. Application of the finite difference method to the solution of a problem for a linear loaded hyperbolic differential equation. *Proceedings of the 8th International Conference on Control and Optimization with Industrial Applications*. Baku, Azerbaijan, 2022, vol. II, pp. 282–284.

6. Ahmedov S.Z., Gasimov R.A., Habibov V.M. Solution of the mixed problem for the non-homogeneous parabolic equation with time derivative in the boundary condition. *Advances in Mathematical Models and Applications*, 2025, Vol. 10, No. 1.

7. Əhmədov S.Z., Xankişiyeva A.X., Nəzərov X.Ə. Bir nöqtədə yüklənməyə malik parabolik tip diferensial tənlik üçün bir qarışıq məsələnin həlli.

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